

An Arabinoxylan Extracted by 18% Alkali from Pea-skin (*Pisum Sativum*)

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The polysaccharide, extracted from pea-skin by 18% sodium hydroxide solution, contains D-xylose and L-arabinose in the ratio of 15:1. The hydrolysate of the fully methylated arabinoxylan yields 2,3,5-tri-O-methyl-L-arabinose, 2, 3-di-O-methyl-D-xylose and 2-O-methyl-D-xylose in the molar ratio of 1:14.1:1.1 and a trace of 2, 3, 4-tri-O-methyl-D-xylose. These data throw some light on the structure of the arabinoxylan obtained.

The arabinoxylan, extracted by 4% alkali solution from pea-skin, has been reported¹ to contain 1 → 4 linked D-xylopyranose residues in the main chain with single-unit side chains of L-arabinose linked to C₃ position of every fifth xylose residue of the main chain. The residue, left after extraction with 4% alkali solution, was subjected to extraction with 18% sodium hydroxide solution. The polysaccharide, thus obtained, contained L-arabinose and D-xylose in the ratio of 1:15. The fact that the amount of xylose increases with increasing strength of alkali used for extraction, leads to the speculation that the pea-skin either contains a series of arabinoxylans with varying lengths of repeating units or a xylan in addition to one or more arabinoxylans. In order to investigate this aspect, a structural study of 18% alkali-extracted polysaccharide has been undertaken.

The polysaccharide having specific rotation -92.2° (in 4% NaOH solution) was subjected to purification by repeated copper-complex formation^{2,6}. The polysaccharide, isolated after each purification, was found to contain xylose and arabinose in the same ratio as in the unpurified sample, thereby indicating the homogeneity of the material.

The purified polysaccharide was methylated first by Haworth's method⁷ and then by Purdie's method⁸ to yield a fully methylated, yellow, glassy product which showed no hydroxyl band in the IR spectrum (OMe, 38.4%; $[\alpha]_D^{25} -56.4^\circ$ in chloroform). After methanolysis and hydrolysis of the methylated polysaccharide, the mixture of methyl sugars on paper chromatographic examination provided spots corresponding to 2,3,5-tri-O-methyl-L-arabinose, 2,3-di-O-methyl-D-xylose and 2-O-methyl-D-xylose together with a trace of 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-D-xylose.

The mixture was separated into its pure components on sheets of Whatman No. 3MM papers and the pure components, viz, 2,3,5-tri-O-methyl-L-arabinose, 2,3-di-

1. Banerji and Rao, *Canad. J. Chem.* (in press)
2. Smith and Srivastava, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 1715.
3. Salkowski, *Ber.*, 1894 **27**, 497.
4. Haworth *et al.* *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 784.
5. Andrews *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1952, 2744.
6. Bebers and Smith, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 6097.
7. Haworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 197, 8.
8. Purdie and Irvine, *ibid.*, 1903, **83**, 1021.

2-O-methyl-D-xylose, were characterised through their specific rotation and preparation of crystalline sugars or their derivatives.

A small quantity of the mixture was separated by quantitative paper chromatography and the relative amounts of trimethylarabinose, dimethyl- and monomethyl-xylose were estimated by the alkaline hypiodite method as 1:14.1:1.1.

From the results of methylation studies it can be concluded that the arabinoxylan, extracted by 18% alkali solution, contains 1 → 4 linked D-xylopyranose residues as the main chain with L-arabinofuranose units occupying the non-reducing end-groups linked glycosidically to C₃ position of some of the xylose molecules. The average length of the repeating unit works out to be 16 anhydro-pentose molecules. From the comparison of the structures of the two arabinoxylans, extracted by 4% and 18% alkali solutions from pea-skin, it can be reasonably concluded that the arabinose residue is present as a single-unit side chain. The difference between these two polysaccharides is in the average lengths of the repeating units. The pea-skin contains a series of arabinoxylans of similar structures but having different repeating units. The difference in behaviours of these polysaccharides towards the strength of the extracting alkali solutions cannot, however, be explained in the light of the present knowledge.

EXPERIMENTAL

All specific rotations are equilibrium values. Unless otherwise stated, all evaporations were carried out *in vacuo* at 30-40°. The solvent mixtures (v. v) used for partition chromatography of sugars and their derivatives were:

- (A) Ethyl acetate : pyridine : water (8:2:1).
- (B) Butanolⁿ: acetic acid : water (4:1:5), upper layer
- (C) Butanolⁿ: benzene : pyridine : water (5:1:3:3), upper layer.
- (D) Benzene : ethanol : water (169:47:15), upper layer.
- (E) Methyl ethyl ketone-water azeotrope.
- (F) Butanolⁿ: ethanol : water (4:1:5), upper layer.

Whatman No. 1 filter papers were used for paper partition chromatography. The spray reagents used were (a) aniline oxalate (saturated aqueous solution) and (b) aniline hydrogen phthalate.

Isolation of the Polysaccharide.—Pea-skins were extracted successively with a boiling mixture of benzene-ethanol, hot water, 0.1% and 4% alkali solutions. The residue, left after the extractions, was treated twice with 18% NaOH solution (500 ml, each time) for 18 hours at the room temperature while shaking in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The resulting slurry was filtered through a piece of nylon cloth. The combined filtrate was acidified with acetic acid to pH 4-5 in the cold (0-5°) and the polysaccharide was precipitated with acetone (1500 ml). The polysaccharide, thus obtained, was dialysed against distilled water for 10 days to remove inorganic salts and again precipitated with acetone. The precipitate was filtered, triturated with absolute ethanol and ether, and finally dried; yield 0.8%; ash, 2.04%; moisture, 11.1%; pentosan, 97.2%; specific rotation—92.2° in 4% NaOH solution.

Hydrolysis and Identification of Xylose and Arabinose.—The polysaccharide (1 g.) was hydrolysed with 2*N*-H₂SO₄ in a boiling water bath for 18 hours, when the hydrolysis, which was followed iodometrically, was found to be complete. The solution was neutralised with barium carbonate, filtered, deionised with Amberlite IR-120(H) and Amberlite IR-45(OH)*, and concentrated to a thin syrup. On paper chromatographic examination of the syrup, using solvents (A, B, and C), xylose and arabinose were detected. A portion of the syrup (200 mg.) was separated on filter paper by solvent A. The dry syrup corresponding to D-xylose was crystallised from dry ethanol; m.p. and mixed m.p. 144-45°, [α]_D²⁰ +19° (c, 1 in water) (lit.⁹ reports +18°).

The syrup corresponding to L-arabinose was dried and crystallised from dry ethanol; m.p. and mixed m.p. 155-57°; [α]_D²⁰ +105° (c, 1 in water) (lit.¹⁰, +103°).

Quantitative Estimation of D-Xylose and L-Arabinose.—The polysaccharide (0.1023 g.) was hydrolysed in the above manner. An aliquot of the hydrolysate, obtained after neutralisation, filtration, and concentration and containing D-ribose as reference sugar, was separated quantitatively by the paper chromatography, using solvent A. The zones corresponding to each sugar were eluted in the usual way and the amounts of the sugars estimated by the periodate method¹¹; xylose and arabinose were found to be present in the ratio of 15:1.

Purification of the Polysaccharide.—The polysaccharide was purified through complexing with Fehling's solution^{12,13}. The arabinoxytan (20 g.) was dissolved in 4% NaOH solution (2 litres) in an atmosphere of nitrogen and freshly prepared Fehling's solution (2 litres) was added when the copper-complex precipitated. The precipitate was filtered, washed, and cold 5*N*-HCl was added to a suspension of the precipitate in water with stirring while the copper-complex decomposed to form a slightly opalescent solution. The polysaccharide was precipitated by adding an equal volume of acetone. The purification process was repeated thrice and the ratio of xylose to arabinose in the substance was estimated after each time and was found to remain unchanged (15:1). [α]_D²⁰ -92.2° (c, 0.5 in 4% NaOH solution).

Methylation of the Arabinoxytan.—The arabinoxytan (2 g.) was methylated first by methyl sulphate and alkali and then by methyl iodide and silver oxide, following the method of Falconer and Adams¹⁴. The methylated product (1.2 g.) had [α]_D²⁰ -56.4° (c, 0.5 in chloroform) and OMe, 38.4% and showed no hydroxyl absorption band in the IR spectrum.

Methanolysis and Hydrolysis of the Methylated Arabinoxytan.—The fully methylated polysaccharide (0.6 g.) was refluxed with 3% methanolic HCl (20 ml) for 18 hours. The syrup, obtained on evaporation, was hydrolysed by heating on a boiling water bath with *N*-HCl, neutralised with silver carbonate, filtered, deionised, and concentrated to a syrup.

Separation and Characterisation of the Components of the Hydrolysate.—The syrup, when examined by paper chromatography, resolved into three spots corresponding to

* A product of Rohm and Haas Company, Pennsylvania, U. S. A.

9. Gillham and Timell, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1956, 36, 410.

10. Aspinall *et al.* *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 1160.

11. Hirst and Jones, *ibid.*, 1949, 1659.

12. Glandsmans and Timell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 80, 1209.

13. Chand *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950 1289.

14. *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1956, 34, 338.

2,3,5-tri-*O*-methyl-*L*-arabinose (R_G 0.96), 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-*D*-xylose (R_G 0.76), and 2-*O*-methyl-*D*-xylose (R_G 0.40). A faint spot of 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-*D*-xylose (R_G 0.94) was also observed (R_G values are with reference to 2, 3, 4, 6-tetra-*O*-methyl-*D*-glucose in solvent F).

The mixture of methyl sugars (ca, 520 mg.) was separated on Whatman No. 3MM filter papers using solvent E. The strips corresponding to tri-, di-, and mono-*O*-methyl sugars were marked by guide spots. The sugars were eluted with water and evaporated to syrups.

The trimethyl fraction was further separated on paper chromatograms in two fractions, one being in a very small quantity. The major fraction on demethylation provided arabinose together with some partially demethylated sugars. The syrup (about 25 mg.) was oxidised with bromine and was converted into the lactone. The 2, 3, 5-tri-*O*-methyl-*L*-arabinoamide was prepared from the lactone in the usual way and was recrystallised from acetone-ether; m.p. and mixed m.p. 129-30° (lit.¹⁵ m.p. 130-32°).

The other trimethyl fraction, viz., 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-*D*-xylose, was obtained in a trace quantity and no further characterisation could be attempted to identify it, except through its R_G value.

The di-*O*-methylxylose component, having $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 24.1^\circ$ (c , 0.25 in water), was refluxed with ethanolic aniline for 6 hours and the *N*-phenyl-2,3-di-*O*-methyl-*D*-xylosylamine obtained was worked up in the usual way; m.p. and mixed m.p. 120-22° (lit.¹⁶ m.p. 123-24°).

The 2-*O*-methylxylose component, having $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 34.1^\circ$ (c , 0.25 in water), was crystallised from methanol-water; m.p. and mixed m.p. 128-29° (lit.¹⁶ m.p. 130°).

Estimation of Methyl Sugars.—A small quantity (10 mg.) of the mixture of methyl sugars was separated quantitatively by paper chromatography, using solvent E. Each sugar was eluted in the usual way and the amount estimated by alkaline hypiodite method¹⁷. The molar ratio of different sugars was as follows:

2,3,5-tri-*O*-methyl-*L*-arabinose; 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-*D*-xylose; 2-*O*-methyl-*D*-xylose as 1: 14.1 : 1.1. 2,3,4-Tri-*O*-methyl-*D*-xylose was present in negligible amounts.

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15. Aspinall and Ferrier, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 638.

16. Aspinall and Sturgeon, *ibid.*, 1957, 4489.

17. Hirst *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1949, 928.